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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

The Use of Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in the Development of Critical Thinking	16
<i>Gulnar Atakhanova Orinbaevna</i>	
Current Aspects of Designing and Implementing Extracurricular Educational Activities at the Primary General Education Level.....	20
<i>Amankosova Dinara Gabitovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida tarbiyachi shaxsiyati va kasbiy mahorati shakllanishining nazariy asoslari....	24
<i>Axmadaliyeva Moxlaroy To'xtapolatovna</i>	
Pedagogical Model and Stages of Teaching Subjects Through a Project-Based Approach	28
<i>Bannayev Qosimjon</i>	
Lotin tili va zamonaviy tibbiy terminologiya: tarixi, vazifasi va amaliy ahamiyati	31
<i>Eshmurodova Shirin Oybekovna</i>	
Motor alaliyaning nonutqiy simptomatikasi	34
<i>Isayeva Mushtariy Alisher qizi</i>	
Talabalar etnomadaniy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik omillari	38
<i>Isomiddinov Asliddin Baxriddin o'g'li</i>	
Texnologiya darslarida o'quvchilarning texnik savodxonligini robototexnika elementlari asosida rivojlantirish.....	41
<i>Jabborova Umida</i>	
Fizika fanini mutaxassislik fanlari integratsiyasi asosida o'qitishda bo'lajak muhandislarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	45
<i>Xayrullayev Asliddin Isatullayevich</i>	
Talaba tomonidan mutaxassislik tilini o'zlashtirishda monologik nutqni o'rgatishning samarali usullari masalasi haqida.....	51
<i>Karimov N. M.</i>	
Zamonaviy pedagog kadrlar tayyorlashda kasbiy motiv va motivatsiyaning o'rni	54
<i>Melikova Elnora Shuxratovna</i>	
Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashda pragmatik kompetensiyaning roli.....	58
<i>Mustafayeva Nilufar Ulashovna</i>	
O'quvchilarda iqtisodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishning pedagogik strategiyalari	62
<i>Nishonova Dilafuz</i>	
Computer-Based Formative Assessment: Advantages and Challenges in Teaching English to High School Students	66
<i>Obidjonova Shokhista Bakhtiyorovna</i>	
Metata'lim texnologiyalari asosida bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim mutaxassislarini tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	70
<i>O'rolboyeva Durdona Sayfiddin qizi</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt asosidagi darslarning an'anaviy darslarga nisbatan samaradorligini qiyosiy tahlil qilish.....	73
<i>Rasulev Bobirjan Atxamovich</i>	
Pedagogik faoliyatda pedagogning kasbiy taraqqiyoti motivatsiyasining psixologik xususiyatlari	78
<i>Rustamova Surayyo Shaxobiddinovna</i>	
Innovatsion kompetentlik tushunchasi va uning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari.....	84
<i>Soliyev Eliyor Ravshan o'g'li</i>	
Nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar eshituv idrokini o'yinlar yordamida rivojlantirishning samarali usullari	88
<i>Xalilova Shahnoza</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'limda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning o'rni va ahamiyati.....	92
<i>Yaqubova Nigoraxon Ibrohimjon qizi</i>	
Soliq yuki – mamlakat soliq soliq tizimining asosiy mezonidir	97
<i>Suyunov Otabek Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish va takomillashtirish yo'llari	101
<i>Ibodova Sarvinoz Sayfilloyevna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida hospital pedagogika fanini o'qitishning dolzarb masalalari va uning uslubiy ta'minoti	106
<i>Inogamova Dilfuza Rahmatullaevna</i>	

Chizma geometriya va kompyuter grafikasi: an'anaviy fan va zamonaviy texnologiyaning uyg'unlashuvi .	111
<i>Raximov A. M., Tairova N. S., Sabirova D. U., Xasanova S. T., Tashpulatov R. X.</i>	
Геймификация в обучении английскому языку на начальном этапе обучения	114
<i>Курбанова Назира Низомиддиновна</i>	
Talabalarda tanqidiy va evristik fikrlashni shakllantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni	117
<i>Adjdiyev Nayrullo Nazrulloevich</i>	
Konstruktiv yondashuv asosida tabiiy fanlar (science)ni o'qitish metodikasi.....	122
<i>Amirullayeva Barno Abdulhaqovna</i>	
Kimyo o'qitishda o'quvchilarning ijodiy faoliyatini shakllantirishning tajriba-sinov natijalari.....	126
<i>Artiqov Maqsud Bahodirovich, Babanazarova Ayzada Omirbaevna</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarni bilingvist sifatida shakllantirishda til o'rganish ko'nikmalari va kompetentsiyalarining rivojlanishi	131
<i>Axmadjonova Gulira'no Muxtorjon qizi</i>	
Talabalarning ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda kooperativ ta'limning metodik yondashuvlari.....	135
<i>Botiraliyeva Gulobar Mahamadismoil qizi</i>	
Talabalarni intellektual faoliyatga tayyorlashda ijtimoiy sherikchilikning pedagogik va metodik asoslari	139
<i>Dilbarjonov Avazbek Ravshanbek o'g'li</i>	
Teacher-Centered and Child-Centered Methods in Early Childhood Education: Insights From Finland and Uzbekistan	143
<i>Djaparova Gulnoza</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida "Metodik mahorat kuni" va "Metodik mahorat soati"ni tashkil etish	150
<i>Do'stov Davron Zulhaydarovich</i>	
Theoretical, Methodological, and Practical Factors of Differentiated Education	155
<i>Ergash Shonazarovich Khasanov</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning intellektual qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda kognitiv yondoshuv	160
<i>Gulbahor Xamidova</i>	
Mustaqil ta'lim – mustahkam bilim.....	164
<i>Halima Shukurova Sunatullayevna</i>	
Integrating Google Classroom and Project-Based Learning for Enhanced Synchronous and Asynchronous Education.....	168
<i>Inomkhojaeva Shodiyakhon Abdukodirkhoja qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarning innovatsion fikrlash ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	174
<i>Mamadaliyev Axadjon G'aniboyevich</i>	
Hududiy rivojlanishda innovatsion yondashuvlarni strategik boshqaruvga integratsiya qilish yo'llari.....	177
<i>Mo'minov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li</i>	
O'rta yoshdagi ayollarda harakat faoliyatini rivojlantirishda milliy o'yinlarning pedagogik ahamiyati	184
<i>Mustafoev Sherali</i>	
Pedagogical and Psychological Foundations of Developing Higher-Order Thinking Skills in Students.....	188
<i>Nasimova Zarina Isomiddin kizi</i>	
Pedagogik ijodkorlikning kasbiy professionallikda namoyon bo'lish xususiyatlari.....	193
<i>Numonova Dildor Umurzoqovna</i>	
Ko'zi oqiz boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini o'rganishning nazariy asoslari	196
<i>Qarshiboyev Asliddin</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil etish masalalari.....	200
<i>Qilichova Marxabo Xudayqulovna</i>	
The Transformation of Existential Thought in British Literature: Iris Murdoch's Philosophical Humanism and the Reinterpretation of Freedom	204
<i>Rahmonqulova Zarnigor Nasimjon qizi</i>	
Sportchilarning elektron platformalardan foydalanishning metodik tahlili	209
<i>Saydullayev Zafar Erkinovich</i>	
Adabiy ta'limda estetik tarbiya	216
<i>Sharipov Elmurod Sa'dulla o'g'li</i>	
O'qituvchi-trenerning ko'p qirrali kasbiy-pedagogik funksiyalari	220
<i>Sulaymonov Jaxongir Solijonovich</i>	
Uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanishda art-pedagogikaning o'qituvchilar hissiy farovonligiga ta'siri	223
<i>Suvanova Kamola Raimqul qizi</i>	

Raqamlashtirish muhitida umumta'lim maktablarida ta'lim sifatini oshirish	226
<i>Xamidova Komila Maxmudovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda kvest texnologiyasi yordamida fizika fanining murakkab tushunchalarini o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish metodikasi.....	231
<i>Yo'ichiyev Shaxriyor Xusanovich, O'rinboyeva Kumushoy Sultonbek qizi</i>	
Совершенствование профессиональных компетенций будущих инженеров на основе интегративного подхода	235
<i>Умарова Гулчехра Абитовна</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarning aqliy qobiliyatining psixologik xususiyatlari	238
<i>Alanazarova Sholpan Artikbaevna, Artiqbaeva Miyassar Jumanazarovna</i>	
Biologiya ta'limida innovatsion metodlarni joriy etishda ta'lim menejmentining roli.....	241
<i>Allayorova Maloxat Normaxmat qizi</i>	
Integrating Innovative Technologies for the Enhancement of Speech and Communication Skills Among Learners With Intellectual Disabilities in Uzbekistan: Pedagogical Approaches and Developmental Outcomes	244
<i>Donisheva Gulruy Akhrorkulovna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini o'quvchilar o'qish savodxonligini rivojlantirishga metodik jihatdan tayyorlash.....	247
<i>Doniyarov Mavlonbek Arabovich</i>	
Kimyoviy birikmalarda bog'lar sonini hisoblashning yangi matematik usullari.....	252
<i>Ergashev Vahob Ergashevich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	257
<i>G'aniyeva Maftuna Abduaziz qizi</i>	
Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida steam fanlarini raqamli texnologiyalar asosida o'qitishning metodik asoslari	261
<i>Jamolova Sitara Muzaffar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining matematik tafakkurini rivojlantirishda didaktik o'yinlar va interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish samaradorligi	264
<i>Mamadiyurov Jamol</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida talabalar mustaqil faoliyatini rivojlantirishda pedagogik yondashuvlar.....	268
<i>Mamayusupova Nafisa Abdulatifovna</i>	
Para yengil atletikachilarda nayza uloqtirish texnikasini takomillashtirish uslubiyati	271
<i>Qiyomova Shohsanam Yarash qizi</i>	
Difficulties in Enhancing Communicativeness of Pre-Service English Teachers.....	275
<i>Kurbonova Maftuna Fakhriddinovna, Mirzayeva Gulshan Azamatovna</i>	
Principles of Teaching Basic Foreign Language Skills (EFL)	278
<i>Samandarova Gulsara Ismatilloevna</i>	
O'quvchilarning innovatsion ta'lim muhitida tayanch kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning dolzarbligi	282
<i>Toshpulatova Farida Radjabovna</i>	
Корпоративная культура педагогов и внутренняя стабильность ДОО	286
<i>Буранова Шохноза Абдуразаковна</i>	
Развивать личностные качества учащихся на уроках географии.....	290
<i>Шадиева Нигора Шариповна</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida oliy ta'lim sifatini oshirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar	295
<i>Baytileuova Gulnaz Quralbay qizi</i>	
Yangi avlod pedagoglarini tayyorlash: kompetensiyalar va qadriyatlarining roli.....	298
<i>Ro'ziboyeva Ma'mura Abdunabiyevna</i>	
Astronomiya fanini o'qitishda integrativ yondashuvdan foydalanib o'qitishning ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni	301
<i>Barakayeva Sarvinov To'iqunovna</i>	
Alohida e'tiborga muhtoj bolalar bilan ishlashda yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash.....	305
<i>Usmonov Salohiddin Dushan o'g'li, Namozova Sevinch Asqar qizi</i>	
Ma'naviy-axloqiy sifatlarni tarbiyalashda pedagogik qadriyatlarining ustuvorligi.....	310
<i>Jumayeva Gulnara Tursunpulatovna</i>	
Talabalarni maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarini maqsadli boshqarishga tayyorlashning nazariy asoslari	314
<i>Mahmudova Zulfiya Xomitovna</i>	
Pedagogical Methodology Improve Students' Professional Mobility in Acquisition of Specialty.....	319
<i>Khidirova Muhabbat Murodillayevna</i>	

Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish	322
<i>Ismoilova Surmaxon Amonovna, Yusupova Mohinur</i>	
Qoraqalpoqlarning dehqonchilik marosimlari	326
<i>Orinboyeva Go'zal Polatovna</i>	
The Complexity of Training Teaching Staff for Work in Public Schools Organized in Medical Stations in Uzbekistan.....	330
<i>Inogamova Dilfuza Rakhmatullaevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim texnologiya fanini o'qitishda STEM yondashuvi orqali o'quvchilarda mustaqil va tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.....	335
<i>Jabbarova Zuhra Omondullayevna</i>	
Eshitishda nuqsoni mavjud bolalarni nutqini shakllantirish metodikasi	338
<i>Z. N. Mamarajabova</i>	
5–7-sinf qizlarida raqamli texnologiyalar ta'sirida tarbiya jarayonining o'ziga xosliklari.....	341
<i>Abdurazoqova Marg'uba Muhammad qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda emotsional intellektni rivojlantirish diagnostikasi: metodlar va natijalar ..	345
<i>Abduxamidova Dilorom Abdumuminovna</i>	
PISA topshiriqlari asosida o'quvchilarda tadqiqotchilik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	349
<i>Axunjanova Shirmonoy Isroiljonovna</i>	
Bo'lajak surdotarjimonlar uchun faoliyat turlarini tanlashda ko'maklashish	354
<i>Dehqanova Muborakxon G'iyosiddinovna</i>	
Mustaqil ta'limni tashkillashtirishda tarjimadan foydalanish jarayonlari	357
<i>Erkayev Elmira Temirovich</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy faoliyat samaradorligini oshirishda kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlash kompetensiyalarining o'rni.....	361
<i>Jumayeva Muxlisa Shokir qizi</i>	
Tasks, Exercises, and Activities in the English Classroom: Differences, Similarities, and Effective Use	366
<i>Qodirov Olim Odilovich</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kommunikativ kompetentlikni rivojlantirish masalalari	372
<i>Safarova Mohichehra Xonzafarovna</i>	
Malaka oshirish tizimida boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonligini rivojlantirish masalalari.....	376
<i>Saidova Dilnoza Maripovna</i>	
O'zbekiston va Yaponiya dzyudo trenerlarining mashg'ulot jarayonlarini qiyosiy tahlili.....	380
<i>Sharipov Xabibullo Abduqahhorovich</i>	
"Kompyuter lingvistikasi"ning rivojlanish tendensiyasi.....	386
<i>Xusanboyeva Muxlisa Ikrojon qizi</i>	
Педагогические технологии стратегического развития взаимного сотрудничества организаций дошкольного образования и родителей.....	392
<i>Тухлиев Муслимбек Шерзод угли</i>	
Oliy ta'limda inklyuziv ta'lim tizimini joriy etish muammolari	397
<i>Dilbar Nurkeldiyeva</i>	
Ixtisoslashtirilgan ta'lim muasasalarida tarbiyaning o'rni.....	401
<i>Laylo Sharopovna Nurmuxamedova</i>	
Intellektida kamchiligi bo'lgan bolalarning ijtimoiylashuvida muloqotning shakllanish xususiyatlari.....	405
<i>Shahnoza Amirsaidova</i>	
Aqli zaif bolalarga ta'lim jarayonida o'yin faoliyatini shakllantirishning ahamiyati.....	409
<i>Ziyodullayeva E'zoza Ne'matjonovna</i>	
Pedagogik texnologiyalar metodlarini tanlash va qo'llashning umumiy mezonlari	412
<i>Abdullayeva Komila Tursunovna</i>	
Didaktik o'yinlar vositasida 2-sinf o'quvchilarida bog'lanishli nutq ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	416
<i>Askarova Gulayim Arislan qizi</i>	
Yugurib kelib uzunlikka sakrovchilarda tezkorlikni samarali va jadal rivojlantirishni ilmiy asoslash.....	420
<i>Avazov Shukrullo Ibatovich, Nuraliyeva O'g'iloy Shomurotovna, Mustafayev Ismoil Nuralio'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda kreativ ta'limning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va zaruriyati.....	425
<i>Axmedova Mastura Jamoliddinovna</i>	
Imkoniyati cheklangan o'quvchilarda tabiatshunoslik kompetensiyasini shakllantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	430
<i>Azizova Dilnora</i>	

Bo'lajak shifokorlarda tibbiy – deontologik kompetensiyalarni shakllanishida tibbiy amaliyotning ahamiyati.....	435
Babadjanova Gulchexra Baxtiyarovna	
Bolaning aqliy rivojlanishini yoritadigan ko'rsatkichlar	440
Bozorboyev Javlon Davlatali o'g'li	
Bo'lajak oligofrenopedagoglarning kasbiy-metodik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish xususiyatlari.....	445
Daminova Maftuna Asqarali qizi	
Kreativ pedagogika fani va mantiqiy fikrlash kompetentligi orasidagi bog'liqlik.....	449
Diyora Egamberdiyeva	
Oilani mustahkamlovchi va ajralishiga olib keluvchi omillar	454
Haqberdiyev Jamoliddin Abdug'affor o'g'li	
Quality Management as a Functional and Attributive Characteristic of Modern Management.....	458
Jabbarbergenova Bibimaryam Amangeldievna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining ijodiy faoliyatini rivojlantirishda pedagogik va psixologik jarayonlar	464
Mamedova Maxfuza Erkinovna	
Huquqiy ong va madaniyatni shakllantirishda yuridik ta'limning roli: tahlil va takliflar	470
Mansurova Zilola Akromxonovna	
Pedagogik ta'limda klaster yondashuvi: O'zbekiston va jahon tajribasi	474
Nafisa Tokhirova Dilshod qizi	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning nazariy-pedagogik asoslari: zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovatsion imkoniyatlarning integratsiyasi asosida shakllanish jarayoni.....	478
Norqulov Lutfullo Mamarajabovich	
Montessori metodikasi va undagi bolalar sensomotorikasini rivojlantirishga doir tajribalar tahlili	484
Parmonova Laylo Iloxomovna	
Molekulyar fizikani modellashtirish orqali o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	488
Q. U. Tog'ayeva	
Milliy tarbiyada raqamli vositalardan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	493
Qo'shnazarova Nozima Maxmutjon qizi	
Learning Intercultural Communication Through Social Media: the Approach of Modern Students	498
Raxmonqulova Feruza Akmal qizi	
Aqliy rivojlanishda muammolari bor maktab o'quvchilarida geometrik tushunchalarni shakllantirishning nazariy asoslar.....	502
Shodiyeva Navbaxor Xabibulla qizi	
Logopedning kasbiy faoliyatida deontologiya va kompetentlikning roli va ahamiyati	506
Temurova Gulchexra Xudoyqulovna, Isomitdinova Shaxinabonu Zavqiddin qizi	
STEAM ta'limida lego konstrukturlarining o'rni va ahamiyati.....	511
Toshpulatova Farida Radjabovna	
Diagnostikasi va rehabilitatsiya qilishda eshitishda nuqsoni bo'lgan bola va ularning ota-onalari bilan bog'liq muammolar.....	514
Toshpulova Nodira Sultonmurod qizi	
Talabalarni maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va ota-onalar hamkorligi o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabat shakllari.....	518
Turdiqulova Luiza Zayniddinovna	
O'zbekistonda ESG tamoyillarining ta'limga integratsiyasi: yutuqlar, muammolar va istiqbollari	522
Tursunova Shahzoda Baxromovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi aqli zaif bolalarning fazoviy tasavvurlarini shakllantirish	526
Xamidova Muyassar Polsaidovna	
Mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etishning asosiy didaktik prinsiplari.....	530
Yuldashev Shukrullo	
Комплексная методика развития и обучения юных футболистов	536
Ортиков Умиджон Худойбердиевич	
Особенности деятельности детей с нарушением зрения	544
Юсупова Назира	
Integration of Music and Language: Creative Approaches to Teaching English to Music Students	548
Akbarova Moxichexra	

Ingliz tilida yozuv malakalarini takomillashtirishda baholash metodikasi.....	553
<i>Alimardonova Malika Botir qizi</i>	
Yosh kurashchilarni jismoniy va aqliy rivojlantirishda basketbol o'yinining ahamiyati	560
<i>Haqnazarov Qurbon Qo'shayevich</i>	
Voleybol murabbiylarining innovatsion fikrlash qobiliyatini shakllantirish usullari	566
<i>Haqqulov Akbar Abdiraupovich</i>	
Sociolinguistic Competence and Intercultural Communicative Competence: Intertwining Concepts and Practical Implications	571
<i>Kuchmurodova Gulnora Khatamovna</i>	
Ilk qadam davlat dasturida steam ta'lim elementlaridan foydalanish imkoniyati	575
<i>Nazarova Aziza Sohib qizi</i>	
Kasbiy rivojlanish jarayonida rahbar shaxsiy sifatlarini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy yo'nalishlari.....	579
<i>Roziqova Nazokat Alisher qizi</i>	
Deontologik yondashuvning nazariy-pedagogik asoslari va uning ta'lim tizimidagi ahamiyati	583
<i>Tashpulatova Nodira Olimjon qizi</i>	
Kasbiy-pedagogik tayyorgarlikda fanlararo integratsiya asosida boshlang'ich ta'lim yo'nalishi o'qituvchilarining metodik salohiyatini oshirish yo'llari.....	586
<i>Xashimova Aziza Alisherovna</i>	
Природа и механизм действия биологических иммуностимуляторов на организм животных	590
<i>Койилова Мехринисо Джураевна</i>	
Badiiy asarlar ustida ishlash jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining emotsional intellektini shakllantirish mezonlari	594
<i>Jamalova Kamola Shahobiddinovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish asosida fizika o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish	600
<i>Musurmonova Shaxnoza Dilshod qizi</i>	
Futbolchilarda texnik tayyorgarlikni takomillashtirishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.....	606
<i>Babayev Anvarjon Axmedovich</i>	

LEARNING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA: THE APPROACH OF MODERN STUDENTS

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Abstract: This scientific article examines the role of social media in developing intercultural communication competence in foreign language education. The study analyzes modern learners' approach to education, particularly their preference for short, interactive, and visual content. It also evaluates the educational potential of popular platforms such as TikTok, YouTube, Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), and Reddit, highlighting their contribution to the development of intercultural competence components such as cultural awareness, empathy, reflection, and social adaptation. The findings emphasize the potential of integrating social media into the educational process as an effective pedagogical tool for simultaneously teaching language and culture.

Key words: intercultural communication, foreign language education, social media, modern learners, TikTok, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter, Reddit, intercultural competence, Byram's model, Dardorff's model.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur ilmiy maqolada xorijiy til ta'limida ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning o'zaro madaniy muloqot kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi roli tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda zamonaviy talabalarning ta'limga yondashuvi, xususan qisqa, interaktiv va vizual kontentga bo'lgan afzalligi o'rganilgan. Shuningdek, TikTok, YouTube, Instagram, X (ilgari Twitter) va Reddit kabi mashhur platformalarning o'quv jarayoniga qo'shadigan imkoniyatlari hamda ular madaniy ong, empatiya, refleksiya va ijtimoiy moslashuv kabi madaniyatlararo kompetensiya tarkibiy qismlarini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati ko'rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari ijtimoiy tarmoqlarni ta'lim jarayoniga integratsiya qilish til va madaniyatni bir vaqtning o'zida o'rgatishning samarali pedagogik vositasi bo'lishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyatlararo muloqot, xorijiy til ta'limi, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, zamonaviy talabalar, TikTok, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter, Reddit, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya, Bayram modeli, Dirdorf modeli.

Аннотация: В данной научной статье исследуется роль социальных сетей в развитии межкультурной коммуникативной компетенции в сфере обучения иностранным языкам. Анализируется подход современных учащихся к образованию, в частности их предпочтение краткого, интерактивного и визуального контента. Также рассматривается образовательный потенциал популярных платформ, таких как TikTok, YouTube, Instagram, X (ранее Twitter) и Reddit, и их вклад в развитие компонентов межкультурной компетентности: культурной осведомлённости, эмпатии, рефлексии и социальной адаптации. Результаты подчёркивают потенциал интеграции социальных сетей в образовательный процесс как эффективного педагогического инструмента для одновременного обучения языку и культуре.

Ключевые слова: межкультурная коммуникация, обучение иностранным языкам, социальные сети, современные учащиеся, TikTok, YouTube, Instagram, Twitter, Reddit, межкультурная компетентность, модель Байрама, модель Дирдорфа.

INTRODUCTION

The new generation of students cannot concentrate on one thing for a long time during the educational process. This is their uniqueness: they prefer to learn new knowledge not by reading traditional books or listening to long lectures, but through short videos and current trends on social networks. As Almudena Márquez Indias points out, "it is necessary to fully exploit technological advances in education to involve students in online communication and collaboration. This will shed light on the digital revolution and its impact on our daily lives" (Márquez Indias, 2022).

Culture is the sum of the spiritual, material, intellectual, and emotional characteristics of a society or social group. Important aspects such as art and literature, lifestyle, value system, traditions, and beliefs all fall within the scope of culture (UNESCO, 2002). When learning a foreign language, it is also important to study the

culture of the speakers of that language, as culture is an integral part of communication (Martin & Nakayama, 2017).

Intercultural communicative competence occupies an important place in modern language education. This competence represents the ability of a person to communicate effectively and flexibly with representatives of other cultures. One of the most important theoretical foundations of this concept is the model put forward by Michael Byram, which explains intercultural competence through five main components: social experience, cultural knowledge, the ability to think and evaluate, communication and expression through language, and the willingness to develop one's knowledge and skills.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Intercultural communication competence has been widely studied as a fundamental component of foreign language education. Byram in 1997 developed a model that emphasizes five key elements: attitudes, knowledge, skills of interpreting and relating, skills of discovery and interaction, and critical cultural awareness. This framework has become the basis for many subsequent studies, highlighting that language learning cannot be separated from cultural understanding. Deardorff in 2006 further expanded this idea, presenting a process-oriented model where intercultural competence is seen as a continuous development of respect, openness, and adaptability.

The rapid growth of social media has introduced new opportunities for intercultural learning. Godwin-Jones in 2018 noted that platforms such as YouTube and Twitter allow learners to engage in authentic communication and observe cultural practices directly from native speakers. Similarly, Martin and Nakayama in 2017 emphasized that digital interaction creates a real context for cultural discourse, making it possible for students to reflect on their own cultural identity while learning from others. Research also indicates that short, visual, and interactive content enhances learners' motivation and attention, aligning with the habits of the modern generation.

In Uzbekistan, scholars have also stressed the integration of modern technologies into language education. Gulomova in 2022 underlined the role of authentic materials and digital tools in developing sociolinguistic awareness among students. Recent studies demonstrate that social networks not only improve linguistic competence but also foster empathy, tolerance, and intercultural awareness. These findings suggest that combining Byram's and Deardorff's theoretical approaches with modern platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and Reddit can provide an effective methodology for building intercultural communication competence in foreign language learning.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this study is based on qualitative and quantitative approaches. Data were obtained through surveys conducted among university students and direct observations of their use of social media platforms for language learning. The collected information was analyzed using comparative and descriptive methods to identify patterns, evaluate intercultural competence development, and interpret learners' attitudes toward digital educational tools.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In Byram's approach, language and culture are considered as an inseparable whole, that is, learning a foreign language cannot be complete without a deep understanding of the culture of the speakers of this language (Byram, 1997). In this regard, language is considered not only as a means of communication, but also as a system that conveys cultural codes. In Darla Deardorff's competency model, qualities such as "cultural awareness," "patience," and "internal reflection" play a key role (Deardorff, 2006). Social networks teach these skills based on real experience: users encounter other views, values, and customs through posts, videos, and comments from representatives of a foreign culture. This, in turn, activates the processes of internal analysis, acceptance, or attempts to understand.

To date, one of the most convenient and popular tools for developing intercultural communication competence is social networks. Platforms such as TikTok, YouTube, Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), and Reddit are not just spaces for communication, but also real, live stages where different cultures are directly reflected. On these networks, people from different ethnicities openly display their lifestyles, values, customs, and even humor. It is this openness that helps to build competence components such as intercultural awareness, empathy, and tolerance.

TikTok is a social network based on the short video format, which allows users to create creative content and share videos about cultural trends, dances, jokes, and daily life. It is popular among young people and is useful for directly seeing and understanding the cultures of different nationalities.

YouTube is the world's largest video platform, which allows users to watch various content (blogs, lessons, interviews, documentaries, etc.) uploaded by other users. It is widely used for language learning and for developing intercultural skills.

Instagram is a social platform for sharing visual content (photos, videos, stories), where users express their lives, traditions, and cultures in visual form. Through the Stories and Reels functions, one can get acquainted with short cultural realities.

X (formerly Twitter) is a microblogging platform where users express their opinions through short posts (tweets) and participate in collective discussions. It allows for real-time communication and observation of cultural discourse for those learning a foreign language.

Reddit is a social platform with a system of topic-based forums (subreddits), where users actively participate in questions and answers, advice, life experiences, and cultural discussions. It creates an interactive space for the exchange of ideas and discussions between global cultures¹.

The results of a survey conducted around the Youth Palace of Creativity to study the relevance of this topic show that the use of social networks among young people is increasing day by day. In particular, young people who are learning a foreign language are using these platforms purposefully. They follow foreign language teachers (for example, Teacher A'zam, Barno Mukimova, Ustozation) on YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok, as well as Uzbek bloggers and journalists living in Canada, the USA, Germany, or Britain. Through this, they not only develop language skills, but also have the opportunity to analyze, understand, and compare similarities and differences between cultures.

According to my personal observations, today's young people are more inclined to learn through short videos, blogs, and interactive content on social networks when learning a language. They actively use modern technologies not only for entertainment purposes, but also to form their ideas about language and culture. Especially through foreign bloggers and foreign experts who create content in the Uzbek language, they have the opportunity to directly observe the lifestyle, daily life, and speech styles of other cultures. Through this, young people not only hear about cultural differences, but also see them in real life, analyze them, and have the opportunity to react to them themselves. In this regard, social networks, especially YouTube, TikTok, and Instagram, are considered important learning tools in the formation of intercultural competence (Godwin-Jones, 2018).

These ideas were also confirmed by practical observations. In particular, in a small survey conducted around the Youth Palace in Tashkent, the majority of 456 respondents (i.e., 85%) admitted that they use social networks for language learning. In their opinion, it is the YouTube and TikTok platforms that are of great help in hearing and seeing the language directly from native speakers and in understanding real communication situations. Although the remaining 15% of participants indicated that they use social networks mainly for entertainment purposes, they also admitted that they increase their knowledge of the language and culture by passively listening to content in a foreign language. The survey results show that young people use these platforms not only as a means of forming linguistic competence, but also as a means of forming cultural competencies.

Social platforms such as X (formerly Twitter) and Reddit provide a convenient space for debate and open discussions between different social groups. Especially for young people who are learning a foreign language, particularly English and its culture, these platforms provide an opportunity to express their thoughts in this language, read posts and comments written by other users, and engage in intercultural dialogue by directly addressing users whose first language is English. For example, through subreddits such as "Ask an American" or "Explain like I'm five" on Reddit, or through global trends on Twitter, the reader understands how people think and what they pay attention to in an environment different from their own culture. This strengthens aspects such as social adaptation, empathy, and communication culture.

In such processes, language serves not only as a tool, but also as a means of understanding cultural positions, values, and social identity. As a result, students have the opportunity to analyze not only linguistic skills, but also cultural and speech characteristics in a particular socio-group context.

This article examines the role of social networks in the formation of intercultural communication competence in foreign language education. The main attention is paid to platforms such as TikTok, YouTube, Instagram, X (formerly Twitter), and Reddit, which are widely used by modern youth. Through these platforms, young people have the opportunity to directly get acquainted with the everyday life, customs, values, and communication styles of representatives of different cultures. During the study, the theoretical foundations of intercultural competence (Byram and Dearsford models) were analyzed, and practical examples were shown of how they can be realistically formed through social networks.

¹ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/TikTok>

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of the above survey showed that young people are actively using these platforms not only for entertainment purposes, but also for language learning and for understanding the cultural context. According to them, it is precisely by listening to short, real-life video content, foreign bloggers, and the direct speech of native speakers that they feel they are developing skills such as cultural awareness, empathy, social adaptation, and reflection. This study confirms that integrating social networks into foreign language education is an effective tool for building not only linguistic, but also intercultural competence. This topic is relevant for the education system and encourages teachers to develop intercultural competence using modern tools. In the future, in foreign language teaching, it is necessary to create wide opportunities for students to master the language and culture as a whole through interactive activities based on social networks, cultural video analysis tasks, virtual discussions, and global online collaboration projects.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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